

Solvent Effect in Acid Hydrolysis of Ethyl Pyruvate

S. C. Rakshit and M. K. Sarkar

The hydrolysis of pyruvic ester in presence of 0.5 *N* hydrochloric acid has been carried out in acetone-water and dioxane-water media at different temperatures under isodielectric conditions. The kinetic data can be reasonably analysed if a simultaneous prevalence of both bi-molecular acyl oxygen scission and unimolecular alkyl oxygen scission mechanisms during the course of the reaction be assumed. Amounts of reaction proceeding via each path together with the thermodynamic functions associated with activation process characterising each mechanism have been evaluated.

The mechanisms of the acid catalysed hydrolysis of esters have been classified^{1,2} under four general heads of which three have been experimentally supported and the fourth is still in need of experimental confirmation. For an ester of the type R-CO₂-R', various factors such as nature of R and R', polar, inductive³ and conjugation effects, unsaturation⁴, stability of carbonium or of oxocarbonium ions⁵, steric factor etc. decide which particular mechanism is operative in any specific case. As is well known the participation of solvent molecule in a reaction, e.g., hydrolysis of esters, generally prevents detection of unimolecular and bimolecular processes in the rate determining step. The use of mixed solvents with different dielectric constants is helpful in such instances. Using such aquo-organic mixed solvent, many esters have recently been shown^{6,7} to proceed simultaneously via two parallel paths of the general classification (*loc. cit.*).

The present investigations concern the effect of mixed solvents (aqueous acetone and aqueous dioxane) on the kinetic quantities of acid catalysed hydrolysis of pyruvic ester carried out at different temperatures under isodielectric conditions. The data obtained have been shown amenable to interpretation which suggests the simultaneous operation of two mechanisms.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl pyruvate (b.p. 56–58°) at pr 20 mm Hg) was prepared in the usual manner. Acetone was purified by a standard procedure⁸. Dioxane was made acid free and distilled before use.

1. C. K. Ingold, "Structure and mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornell University Press, 1953, pp. 752.
2. K. J. Laidler, "Reaction Kinetics", Vol. 2, Pergamon Press, 1963.
3. C. N. Hinshelwood and A. R. Legard, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1558.
E. W. T. Turner and C. N. Hinshelwood, *ibid.*, 1938, 862.
4. K. L. Mallik and M. N. Das, *Naturwiss.*, 1964, 2, 37.
5. H. P. Treffers and L. P. Hammett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 1708. Also see J. Hine, "Physical Organic Chemistry", McGraw Hill Book Co., pp. 278.
6. H. Sadek and F. Y. Khalil, *Z. Physik Chem.*, 1968, 57, 306.
7. K. R. Adams, I. Lauder and V. R. Stimson, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1962, 15, 467.
8. Weissberger *et al.*, *Technique in Organic Chemistry*, Vol. VII, Interscience Publishers, 1955, 381.

Solvent-pairs of different dielectric constants : Dioxane water : The weight percentage compositions of water and dioxane to form media of different dielectric constants at different temperatures are given by Akerlof and Short⁹. These data were suitably utilised in determining the volume compositions of dioxane and water to produce isodielectric media at different temperatures.

Acetone-water : The plots of dielectric constant versus weight per cent of acetone were made for different temperatures by utilising the data¹² on dielectric constant for certain compositions of aqueous acetone in conjunction with the relation¹⁰

$$\log D_1 = \log D_2 + \frac{L}{2.303} (T_2 - T_1)$$

where L = constant characteristic of the solvent and has a value .00463.

D_1 = unknown dielectric constant of acetone-water mixture at temperature T_1 .

D_2 = known dielectric constant of the mixture at temperature T_2 .

Use of these linear graphs together with the density data of acetone at 10°, 20°, 25°, 30° and 35° was made in preparing the final reacting solutions having dielectric constants 69.5, 58, 45.5 and 31.5 at each of the temperatures mentioned.

The kinetic study involved the method of titration. The experiment was conducted in electrically operated thermostat which maintained constant temperature within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Equal volumes of ester (0.2 M) and hydrochloric acid (1 N) solutions were placed in the thermostat for about 1 hr. to attain the temperature of the bath. Experimental solutions were then mixed up and 10 ml portions of the mixture titrated against standard alkali at different time intervals.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the foregoing experiments involving acetone-water and dioxane-water as solvent media are tabulated below. It is found that the experimental data fit a first order-kinetic rate, the rate constants of which appear in Table I.

TABLE I

Acid hydrolysis of Ethyl Pyruvate [Solvent—water]

Temperature (°C)	$k_{obs} \times 10^3$ min	ΔH^* (K.Cals/ gm.mole)	A	ΔS^* (e.u.)	ΔF^* (K.Cals/ gm.mole)
25	11.52				
30	16.96				
35	20.73	16.6	10^{10}	-21.1	23.1
40	27.64				
45	43.66				

9. G. Akerlof and O. A. Short, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1241.
10. E. A. Moelwyn Hughes, *The Kinetics of Reactions in Solution*, Oxford University Press, 1947, pp. 90.
11. E. S. Amis, *Solvent Effects of Reaction Rates and Mechanism*, Academic Press, 1966.
12. E. S. Amis and S. Siegel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 674.

TABLE II

Acid hydrolysis of Ethyl Pyruvate [Solvent—Acetone-water system]

Dielectric constant	Temperature (°C)	$k_{obs} \times 10^3$ min	ΔH^* (K.Cals/ gm.mole)	A	ΔS^* (e.u.)	ΔF^* (K.Cals/ gm.mole)
69.5	10	4.13	12.0	$10^{6.7}$	-36.2	22.8
	20	7.25				
	25	10.02				
	30	14.25				
	35	16.59				
58.0	10	3.72	10.5	$10^{5.6}$	-41.3	22.8
	20	5.91				
	25	8.05				
	30	12.01				
	35	14.47				
45.5	10	3.31	9.2	$10^{4.5}$	-46.3	23.0
	20	4.69				
	25	6.15				
	30	9.32				
	35	11.89				
31.5	10	2.53	8.3	$10^{3.7}$	-50.0	23.2
	20	3.75				
	25	4.92				
	30	6.43				
	35	7.52				

TABLE III

Acid hydrolysis of Ethyl Pyruvate [Solvent—Dioxane-water]

Dielectric constant	Temperature (°C)	$k_{obs} \times 10^3$ min	ΔH^* (K.Cals/ gm.mole)	A	ΔS^* (e.u.)	ΔF^* (K.Cals/ gm.mole)
69.0	25	10.22	15.0	10^9	-25.7	22.9
	30	15.63				
	35	18.42				
	40	25.35				
	45	39.18				
62.5	25	9.18	14.1	10^8	-30.3	23.4
	30	14.40				
	35	16.85				
	40	23.03				
	45	37.30				
49.5	25	8.37	12.9	$10^{7.3}$	-33.5	23.2
	30	12.67				
	35	15.17				
	40	20.72				
	45	33.40				
36.0	25	6.94	12.0	$10^{6.5}$	-37.2	23.4
	30	10.79				
	35	13.81				
	40	18.13				
	45	28.20				
12.0	25	3.90	10.7	$10^{5.5}$	-41.8	23.6
	30	6.20				
	35	10.30				
	40	14.70				
	45	18.87				

It is also noticed from Table II and III that the rate constants vary with the dielectric constant of the medium or in other words with different compositions of the solvent-pair at any definite temperature. It is therefore necessary to critically consider the results on the basis of the role of dielectric constants (and hence solvent compositions) to obtain an interpretation of the rate and other kinetic data and finally to suggest the possible mechanism operating in this hydrolysis process.

A look at Table II and III will at once make one point evident *viz.*, decrease in rate constant with decrease in dielectric constant characterising the different solvent compositions. This is a common phenomenon^{6,11} suggesting the formation of more polar transition states. A peculiar feature however, is the gradual decrease in the energy of activation accompanying the decrease in rate constants as the solvent medium is made richer in organic component *viz.*, acetone or dioxane. Such behaviours, though not very common, are, however, not seldom either and have been reported in literature^{6,12}. Before we try to formulate the mechanism of hydrolysis of pyruvic ester, the consideration of the thermodynamic functions associated with the process of activation in different solvent systems would be worth while. It may be noted that the free energy of activation ΔF^* in different solvent-pair media remains practically the same *viz.*, 22 to 24 K.Cals/gm. mole (Table II and III). There is, of course, a very slow increase in the free energy of activation with the increase in percentage of the organic component of the solvent-pair. An incidental plot of $T\Delta S^*$ against ΔH^* is found to be linear and represents what is known as the "compensation effect".² This enables us to infer, at least, tentatively that

(i) Probably similar transition states are formed in the given range of compositions of the solvent-pair.

(ii) If the hydrolysis proceeds by mixed mechanisms involving parallel avenues of reactions the different transition states which may be present simultaneously are so characterised by heats of activation and entropy of activation as not to impair the 'compensation effect'.

(iii) High and different negative values of entropy of activation are, in general, responsible for the prevention of the parallelism being drawn between the decrease in rate constant with increase in activation energy in the present investigations.

As has been remarked, the over-all reaction rate follows a first order process. To understand the way of its dependence on the composition of the solvent media, plots of $\log k_{obs}$ Vs $\log [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ in moles/litre yield curves indicating no single and unique dependence of the observed rate constant on the concentration of water. It may, therefore, be possible that the observed rate constant for any solvent composition at any temperature is really a superposition of two (or more) rates each depending on different powers of water concentration. To explore this possibility we confine ourselves to the simplest situation and assume the hydrolysis to proceed via at least two independent mechanisms each involving different dependence on water concentration. The splitting of the observed rate constant in two parts is made in the following way (cf. Sadek, Khalil, loc. cit.).

$$k_{obs} = k'_2 + k'_1 = k_2[\text{H}_2\text{O}] + k_1[\text{H}_2\text{O}]^n$$

where n is one of the values 0, 2, 3, 4 etc. excluding 1.

The retention of $k_2[\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ term in the above break-up is guided by the consideration that the commonest type of acid-catalysed ester hydrolyses occurs through acyl-oxygen scission A'_2 mechanism^{1,2,13} with a bimolecular rate-determining step involving one molecule of water in the formation of transition state. To determine the value of n in the second term, trial plots of $k_{obs}/[\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ against $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{n-1}$ at any definite temperature are made for $n = 2, 3, 4$ and it is found that none of the plots yield a straight line. In the case of $n = 0$, however, the plot is equivalent to one of drawing a graph of k_{obs} Vs $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and in practice linear graphs result for different temperatures both for acetone-water solvent-pair and the dioxane-water solvent-pair at different compositions. The temperature range for the former covers the span 10° to 35° and for the latter, 25° to 45° . The bimolecular rate constant k_2 and the unimolecular rate constant k_1 are thus evaluated from the slopes and the intercepts of the resulting lines for the two solvent-pair systems. The percentages of the reaction proceeding via bimolecular and unimolecular mechanisms as well as the energies of activation can thus be calculated and these are recorded in the following Tables IV, V and VI.

TABLE IV

Solvent—Acetone-water system

Observed rate constant k_{obs} (apparent), true (split) second order and first order rate constants k_2 and k_1 , split rate constants k_2' and k_1' of A'_2 and A_1'' mechanisms.

Temperature (°C)	Dielectric constant	Molar conc. of water	rate const. $k_1 \times 10^3 /$ min.	rate const. $k_2 \times 10^4 /$ (lit.mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	$k_1' \times 10^3 /$ min. (A_1'' me- chanism)	$k_2' \times 10^3 /$ min. (A_2' me- chanism)	Percentage of reaction proceeding by,	
							A_2' me- chanism	A_1'' me- chanism
10	Pure water	55.50	2.63	0.374	2.63	2.08	44.2	55.8
	69.5	39.96	"	"	"	1.49	36.2	63.8
	58.0	29.69	"	"	"	1.11	29.7	70.3
	45.5	19.42	"	"	"	0.726	21.6	78.4
	31.5	8.87	"	"	"	0.332	11.1	88.9
20	Pure water	55.50	2.63	1.05	2.63	5.83	68.9	31.1
	69.5	43.80	"	"	"	4.60	63.8	36.2
	58.0	32.71	"	"	"	3.43	56.5	43.5
	45.5	21.62	"	"	"	2.27	46.4	53.6
	31.5	10.53	"	"	"	1.11	29.8	70.2
25	Pure water	55.50	3.38	1.45	3.38	8.05	70.4	29.6
	69.5	44.86	"	"	"	6.51	66.0	34.0
	58.0	33.52	"	"	"	4.86	59.1	40.9
	45.5	22.43	"	"	"	3.25	49.0	51.0
	31.5	11.08	"	"	"	1.61	32.3	67.7
30	Pure water	55.50	3.75	2.35	3.75	13.00	77.7	22.3
	69.5	46.98	"	"	"	11.00	74.6	25.4
	58.0	35.27	"	"	"	8.29	68.8	31.2
	45.5	23.77	"	"	"	5.59	59.9	40.1
	31.5	11.88	"	"	"	2.79	42.7	57.3
35	Pure water	55.50	4.06	2.89	4.06	16.00	80.0	20.0
	69.5	48.86	"	"	"	14.10	77.7	22.3
	58.0	37.00	"	"	"	10.70	72.5	27.5
	45.5	24.58	"	"	"	7.10	63.6	36.4
	31.5	12.42	"	"	"	3.59	47.0	53.0

TABLE V

Acid hydrolysis of Ethyl Pyruvate. Solvent—Dioxane-water system

Temperature (°C)	Dielectric constant	Molar conc. of water	$k_1 \times 10^3 /$ min.	$k_2 \times 10^4 /$ (lit.mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	$k_1' \times 10^3 /$ min. (A_1'' me- chanism)	$k_2' \times 10^2 /$ min. (A_2' me- chanism)	Percentage of reaction proceeding by	
							A_2' me- chanism	A_1'' me- chanism
25	Pure water	55.50	1.80	1.69	1.80	0.938	83.9	16.1
	69.0	49.57	"	"	"	0.838	82.3	17.7
	62.5	45.73	"	"	"	0.773	81.7	18.3
	49.5	37.94	"	"	"	0.641	78.1	21.9
	36.0	29.63	"	"	"	0.500	73.5	26.5
	12.0	13.85	"	"	"	0.234	56.5	43.5
30	Pure water	55.50	2.80	2.54	2.80	1.42	83.5	16.5
	69.0	51.12	"	"	"	1.30	82.3	17.7
	62.5	46.98	"	"	"	1.20	81.1	18.9
	49.5	38.70	"	"	"	0.983	77.8	22.2
	36.0	30.40	"	"	"	0.772	73.4	26.6
	12.0	14.37	"	"	"	0.365	56.6	43.4
35	Pure water	55.50	5.00	2.65	5.00	1.47	74.6	25.4
	69.0	51.91	"	"	"	1.37	73.3	26.7
	62.5	47.49	"	"	"	1.26	71.6	28.4
	49.5	39.49	"	"	"	1.05	67.7	32.3
	36.0	30.91	"	"	"	0.82	62.1	37.9
	12.0	14.63	"	"	"	0.387	43.6	56.4
40	Pure water	55.50	7.00	3.50	7.00	1.94	73.5	26.5
	69.0	52.63	"	"	"	1.84	72.4	27.6
	62.5	48.50	"	"	"	1.70	70.8	29.2
	49.5	40.23	"	"	"	1.41	66.8	33.2
	36.0	31.70	"	"	"	1.11	61.3	38.7
	12.0	14.88	"	"	"	0.52	42.6	57.4
45	Pure water	55.50	9.00	5.90	9.00	3.27	78.4	21.6
	69.0	53.61	"	"	"	3.16	77.8	22.2
	62.5	49.50	"	"	"	2.92	76.4	23.6
	49.5	40.97	"	"	"	2.42	72.9	27.1
	36.0	31.90	"	"	"	1.88	67.6	32.4
	12.0	15.12	"	"	"	0.89	49.7	50.3

It is noticed that at any definite temperature the percentage of reaction along the unimolecular alkyl-oxygen scission-mechanistic path increases with decrease in dielectric constant, while that of A_2' mechanism involving acyl-oxygen scission, it is just the reverse. The effect is more pronounced for aqueous acetone system than for aqueous dioxane system. This kind of observation departs from the pattern observed in tertiary butyl esters^{6,7} where the percentage of reaction along A_1'' mechanism increases with water content. Obviously the starting substances *viz.*, a keto ester in the present case and tertiary butyl ester in their case differ quite a lot in their electronic density distribution at α -carbon, carboxylic carbon and the oxygen atoms and, hence, may exhibit quite different behaviour.

For any given dielectric constant of the solvent-pair it will be noted from the Table VI that the reaction percentage via A'_2 mechanism increases and that via A''_1 mechanism decreases with rise in temperature for acetone-water system. With dioxane-water system, the percentage variations are not similar, nor large and are mostly confined within a rather limited range for both the mechanisms except when the dielectric constant is too low *e.g.*, 12.

The thermodynamic functions associated with the activation process as recorded in Tables I, II, III are apparent. The actual values of free energy of activation, heats of activation and entropies of activation calculated from data in Tables IV and V are presented in Table VI.

TABLE VI
Acid hydrolysis of Ethyl Pyruvate

Medium Dielectric constant	ΔH^* (K.Cals/ gm.mole)	ΔS^* (e.u.)	$T\Delta S^*$ (K.Cals/ gm.mole)	ΔF^* (K.Cals/ gm.mole)	
Dioxane-water system					
Pure water	13.8	-30.3	- 9.3	23.1	} Biomolecular Acyl-oxygen scission mechanism. (A'_2).
69.0	11.1	-39.7	-12.2	22.3	
62.5	10.2	-42.3	-13.0	23.2	
49.5	9.9	-44.0	-13.6	23.5	
36.0	9.4	-45.9	-14.2	23.6	
12.0	8.5	-50.5	-15.6	24.1	
Acetone-water system					
Pure water	14.5	-27.9	- 8.3	22.8	} Unimolecular Alkyl-oxygen scission mechanism (A''_1).
69.5	13.5	-31.8	- 9.5	22.9	
58.0	12.3	-36.7	-10.9	23.2	
45.5	11.8	-38.5	-11.5	23.3	
31.5	11.3	-41.7	-12.4	23.8	
Dioxane-water system					
All Compositions	15.4	-28.5	- 8.8	24.1	} Unimolecular Alkyl-oxygen scission mechanism (A''_1).
Acetone-water system					
Do.	9.5	-46.7	-13.9	23.4	

It may be noted that the magnitudes of the energies of activation for the A'_2 path of the acid hydrolyses are in the range 10 to 14 K.Cals/gm. mole for different dielectric media of the two solvent-pair systems. The average thus hovers around 12 K.Cals/gm.mole. There is thus a deviation of about (4-5) K.Cals/gm.mole from the values of the simple model esters [methyl acetate, ethyl acetate]¹⁴ or those of more complex esters [tertiary butyl esters^{6,7,15}] which have $\Delta H^* \approx 16$ to 17 K.Cals/gm.mole for the A'_2 path. But the data recorded by T. Yrjana¹⁶ tend to be similar to ours. It is, however, important to remember that such comparisons are meaningful only if the corresponding entropies of activation are

14. Vide Ref. 10, pp. 324.

15. S. R. Johns and V. R. Stimson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 467.

16. T. Yrjana, *Soumen Kemistilehti*, 1964, B37. 108.

comparable in magnitudes. In the present investigations, the entropies of activation for both the paths A'_2 and A''_1 are much more negative than those recorded for tertiary butyl esters (loc. cit) or for the model esters (loc. cit). Such high negative values of entropies of activation are due to immobilisation in varying degrees of the solvent molecules around the activated complex due to electrostriction effect. A crude and tentative calculation of the number of solvent molecules divested of their mobility in excess of that of the solvent molecules bound to the reactants can be made for any dielectric medium from a knowledge of the composition of the solvent-pair, the entropy of fusion of ice and the entropy of fusion of the organic component. Referring to the acetone-water medium of dielectric constant^{69.5} (Tables IV and VI) such rough computation yields the electrostriction value per mole of transition state complex as the immobilisation of a mixture of nearly 0.33 moles of acetone and 5 moles of water in excess of that bound to the reactants¹⁷.

Finally the compensation effect, which is basically a relation of the linear free energy type, is found to be valid when applied to ΔH^* and $T\Delta S^*$ terms of Table VI.

A fairly recent work by Anantakrishnan and Radhakrishnamurti¹⁸ shows that for certain basic hydrolyses of esters there exists a linear dependence of $\log k_N$ on mole fraction of water in the aquo-organic solvent. Although there may be a tendency to regard this as a possible correlation factor, we do not deem it any new variant or more fundamental than the well known theoretical correlation between $\log k$ and $1/D$, since the aquo-organic solvent media studied by the authors¹⁸ already possess the linear dependence of $1/D$ on the mole fraction of water.

Physical Chemistry Laboratory,
Burdwan University,
Burdwan, West Bengal.

Received December 12, 1970

17. A. A. Frost and R. G. Pearson, *Kinetics and Mechanism*, Toppan Printing Co., 1961, pp. 134.
18. S. V. Anantakrishnan and P. S. Radhakrishnamurti, *Indian J. Chem.* 1965, 3, 336.